

Studies on Azo-aldehydes.

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The azo-aldehydes form an interesting group of compounds on account of the fact that they may be used as intermediate products in the synthesis of beautiful and useful dyes with multiple chromophores (Green and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1113; Sen and Sett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 111; Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171; Sen and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 487; Sen and Sen, *ibid.*, 1930, 7, 151).

The possibility of preparing hydroxy-azo-aldehydes by Reimer and Tiemann's reaction appears not to have been fully investigated. The only attempt made in this direction appears to be that of Borsche (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1925) and of Borsche and Bolsten (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2094) who obtained benzeneazo-salicylaldehyde and benzeneazo-*o*-cresolaldehyde respectively from the corresponding hydroxy-azo compounds. It, therefore, seemed to be of interest to study the hydroxy-azo-compounds further with a view to derive from them the dyes with multiple chromophores.

The chief difficulty in the preparation of hydroxyazo-aldehydes by Reimer and Tiemann's reaction is due to the fact that most of the hydroxyazo compounds generally are not very soluble in concentrated caustic soda solution, the sodium salts of the azophenols being invariably precipitated. Consequently a comparatively dilute solution (23%) of caustic soda has to be taken which accounts for the rather low yield obtained in these cases. It has been found that a mixture of chloroform and alcohol (1:4), instead of chloroform alone as in the modified method of Sen and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 173) increases the yield to some extent.

The effect of substituents in the phenol residue and in the benzene residue of the azophenols on the yield of the corresponding aldehydes has also been thoroughly investigated.

The yield of the aldehyde from benzeneazoresorcinol is greater than from benzeneazophenol. The reactivity of the hydroxyazo-compounds with an alkyl radical (Me) in the *ortho*-position to the OH group appears to be more or less diminished; and the reactivity is still further diminished by the presence of one alkyl radical in the *ortho*-position and another alkyl radical in the *meta*-position as in the case of benzeneazothymol and benzeneazocarvacrol. It is remarkable to observe that chlorine in the *o*-position to the OH or a NO₂

group in the *o*- or *m*-position to the OH, inhibits the reaction almost completely. It is observed that substituents generally exert a more or less inhibiting effect, it being more marked when substituting groups are present in the phenol residue as is evident from Table I.

TABLE I.

Substituting groups.	In the benzene residue as.	Yield.	In the phenol residue as.	Yield.
NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene-azophenol	7%	Benzeneazo- <i>m</i> -nitrophenol	No reaction
	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene-azophenol	4	Benzeneazo- <i>o</i> -nitrophenol	No reaction
	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene-azophenol	5		
Cl	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzene-azophenol	10	Benzeneazo- <i>o</i> -chlorophenol	No reaction
	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzene-azophenol	10		
Me	<i>o</i> -Tolueneazo-phenol	8	Benzeneazo- <i>o</i> -cresol	4%
	<i>p</i> -Tolueneazo-phenol	8		

With a view to confirm the constitution of the various hydroxy-azo compounds, thus obtained, most of them have been further synthesised by diazotising the corresponding amino compounds and coupling with the corresponding hydroxy aldehydes (*vide* Experimental).

The hydroxyazo-aldehydes exhibit marked inactivity in forming bisulphite compounds and in reducing ammoniacal silver nitrate solution. They give semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones with extreme difficulty.

The shades produced on silk by the azo-aldehydes themselves generally differ very little from that of the corresponding azo compounds. It is, however, interesting to observe that the entrance of a CHO group into benzeneazothymol or benzeneazocarvacrol remarkably diminishes the depth of the colour.

It is noted that the introduction of a nitro group into benzeneazo-salicylaldehyde in *p*-position to the azo-group as in *p*-nitrobenzene-azo-salicylaldehyde or the introduction of an additional OH group into the molecule as in benzeneazodihydroxybenzaldehyde increases the depth of the colour. Thus, while benzeneazo-salicylaldehyde is yellow, *p*-nitrobenzeneazo-salicylaldehyde is yellowish orange and benzeneazo-dihydroxybenzaldehyde is orange. The entrance of a nitro group into the *ortho*- or *meta*-position to the azo-group or the presence of a Cl in the molecule has little or no effect on the depth of

the colour, the corresponding compounds being all yellow. It is noteworthy that the introduction of Me group into benzeneazo-salicylaldehyde has different effect according as the Me group is in the benzene nucleus or phenol residue. Thus *o*- or *p*-tolueneazo-salicylaldehyde having the Me group in the benzene nucleus produces yellow shade on silk while benzene-azo-*o*-cresol-aldehyde with a Me group in the phenol nucleus produces golden yellow shade.

With a view to study the influence of various substituents, *viz.*, OH, NO₂, Me, etc., some of these azo-aldehydes have been successfully condensed with dimethylaniline and resorcin, beautiful dyes of the azotriphenylmethane and azopyronine series being obtained with the two chromophores in *meta*-position to each other. This will form the subject matter of a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzeneazoresorcylic aldehyde.—Benzeneazoresorcin (15 g.) dissolved in a mixture of chloroform (50 c.c.) and alcohol (200 c.c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring to a solution of caustic soda (80 g. in 320 c.c. of water) kept in a flask, fitted with an upright condenser and heated on the water-bath to 60° when the sodium salt of the azo-aldehyde separated out. After stirring for 8 hours the alcohol and the excess of chloroform was distilled off, the sodium salt was collected, dissolved in hot water, and the free hydroxyaldehyde precipitated with acetic acid. Benzeneazoresorcin was separated from the corresponding aldehyde by repeated treatment with large excess of carbon tetrachloride in which the aldehyde is sparingly soluble in cold. It is obtained as micro-crystalline red powder from dilute alcohol, m.p. 231°, yield 3.5 g. It is soluble in chloroform, pyridine, acetone, benzene; sparingly in ether and carbon tetrachloride. It dyes silk with orange shade. (Found: N, 11.63. C₁₃H₁₀O₃N₂ requires N, 11.67 per cent).

The aldehyde is identical with the aldehyde prepared by Borsche and Bolsten (*loc. cit.*) by coupling diazotised aniline with β -resorcylic aldehyde, the mixed melting points being identical. The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from dilute acetic acid and melts at 217° and is identical with the phenylhydrazone obtained by Borsche and Bolsten (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 16.92. C₁₉H₁₆O₂N₄ requires N, 16.86 per cent).

The other aldehydes prepared are described in the Table II.

TABLE II.

Compound.	Prepared from.	M.p.	Shade on silk.	Analysis.		REMARKS.
				Found.	Calc.	
Benzeneazobicyclic-aldehyde	Benzeneazophenol	127°	Yellow	...	...	Golden yellow prisms from alcohol. Identical with the compound described by Tummley (<i>Annalen</i> , 1889, 251, 17) and Borsche (<i>loc. cit.</i>); phenylhydrazone, m.p. 198°.
Benzenezo-o-cresol aldehyde	Benzenezo-o-cresol	76°	Golden yellow	...	...	Brown needles from alcohol; phenyl hydrazone, m.p. 147-48°, identical with the compound, prepared by Borsche and Bolsten (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
Benzeneazothymol aldehyde (C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂)	Benzeneazothymol and from diazobenzene chloride and thymol aldehyde (Sen and Roy, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	178°	Pale yellow	N, 10.36	9.93%	Reddish brown silky needles from alcohol. Soluble in pyridine, acetone, benzene, chloroform; sparingly soluble in alcohol and ether.
Phenylhydrazone (C ₂₃ H ₂₄ ON ₄)		180°	...	N, 15.37	15.05	Crystallised from alcohol, the m.p. considerably depressed when mixed with the corresponding aldehyde.
Benzeneazocarvacrol aldehyde (C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂)	Benzene-azocarvacrol and from diazobenzene chloride and carvacrol aldehyde (preparation of carvacrol-aldehyde described later).	135°	Light yellow	N, 10.39	9.93	Stout needles from alcohol. Soluble in chloroform, benzene, pyridine, acetone; sparingly soluble in alcohol and ether.
Phenylhydrazone (C ₂₃ H ₂₄ ON ₄)		225°		N, 15.39	15.05	Crystallised from dilute acetic acid.

TABLE II—(contd.)

Compound.	Prepared from.	M.p.	Shade on silk.	Found.	Analysis.	Remarks.
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzenesalicylaldehyde (C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃)		192°-93°	Orange yellow			Reddish brown needles from toluene identical with the compound prepared by Hewitt and Mitchell (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1907, 91, 1263); phenylhydrazone melts at 235°-240°.
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzenesalicylaldehyde (C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃)	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzenesophenol and from disozised- <i>m</i> -nitroaniline and salicylaldehyde	169°	Yellow	N, 15.55	15.50%	Red needles from alcohol. Highly soluble in chloroform, alcohol, acetone, pyridine; sparingly soluble in CCl ₄ , petroleum ether.
<i>Semicarbazone</i> (C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃)	...	248°	...	N, 26.07	25.61	Crystallised from alcohol.
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzenesalicylaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzenesophenol	141°	Yellow	...	...	Red needles from alcohol. Identical with the compound obtained by Grandmoulin and Freiman (<i>J. pr. Chem.</i> , 1908, ii, 76, 384); phenylhydrazone melts at 192°.
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzenesalicylaldehyde (C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl)	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzenesophenol also from <i>p</i> -chlorodiazobenzene chloride and salicylaldehyde	198°	Yellow	N, 11.54	10.75	Yellow plates from alcohol. Highly soluble in chloroform, pyridine, acetone, benzene, sparingly soluble in CCl ₄ .
<i>Semicarbazone</i> (C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl)	...	Does not melt below 900°	...	...	...	Crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE II—(contd.)

Compound.	Prepared from.	M.p.	Shade on silk.	Analysis.		REMARKS.
				Found.	Calc.	
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzeneazo-salicylaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzeneazophenol and from <i>o</i> -chlorodiazobenzene chloride and salicylaldehyde	184°	Yellow	N, 11.65	10.74%	Fern-like crystals from alcohol, highly soluble in chloroform, ether, acetone, pyridine, benzene, moderately soluble in CCl ₄ and alcohol; insoluble in petroleum ether.
<i>Semicarbazone</i>	...	259°	...	...	...	Crystallised from alcohol.
<i>p</i> -Tolueneazosalicylaldehyde (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂)	<i>p</i> -Tolueneazophenol and from <i>p</i> -methyldiazobenzene chloride and salicylaldehyde	147°	Yellow	N, 11.13	11.60	Micro-crystalline yellow powder from alcohol, highly soluble in chloroform, benzene, alcohol, pyridine, acetone, CS ₂ ; sparingly soluble in petroleum ether.
<i>Semicarbazone</i> (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₅)	...	250°	Yellow	N, 23.79	23.57	Crystallised from alcohol.
<i>o</i> -Tolueneazosalicylaldehyde.	<i>o</i> -Toluene-azo-phenol also from <i>o</i> -methyl azobenzene chloride and salicylaldehyde.	120°	Yellow	N, 11.40	11.66	Yellow needles from alcohol, highly soluble in chloroform, CCl ₄ , acetone, pyridine, benzene, alcohol, ether, petroleum ether, CS ₂ .
<i>Semicarbazone</i>	...	196°	...	N, 23.27	23.57	Crystallised from alcohol.

Preparation of carvacrol aldehyde.—A solution of carvacrol (15 g.) in a mixture of chloroform (16 c. c.) and alcohol (50 c. c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring to a solution of caustic soda (20 g. in 83 c. c. of water) which was kept in a flask fitted with an upright condenser. The reaction was carried at 40° for 10 hours. The alcohol and the excess of chloroform was driven off and the solution made strongly acidic when a deep red oil separated out. The mixture was distilled in steam when the aldehyde separated as a reddish oil in the distillate which was taken up with ether and purified through the bisulphite compound in the usual way. Deep red liquid boiling at 237°; soluble in alcohol and ether, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 8.01. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.15; H, 7.86 per cent). This is the *ortho*-aldehyde as it is volatile with steam and gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The *p*-aldehyde seems not to be formed in this case. The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 252°. (Found: N, 18.10. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.86 per cent).

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On Ketimine-enamine Compounds.

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In the literature differences of opinion with regard to the mode of behaviour of ketimine-enamine tautomeric compounds in condensation reactions are largely in evidence, where the main issue has been whether the compounds react in their ketimine form (*cf.*, Burns, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1893, *ii*, 47, 105; Meyer, *Chem. Centr.*, 1908, *II*, 591), or are active in their enamine phase (Combes and Combes, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1893, *iii*, 7, 778; Benary, Reiter and Soenderop, *Ber.*, 1917, *50*, 83). Even phenylcarbimide, a reagent which appears to have little effect upon the different isomers when dissolved in a non-ionising solvent, reacts (*cf.* Behrend and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1900, *33*, 621) with both forms of the above tautomeric compounds. Consequently they